

RESEARCH ARTICLE ↓

Influence of Human Capital Development on the Continuity of Selected Family Business in South East, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the influence of human capital development on the continuity of selected family business in Enugu State Nigeria while the following specific objectives are; to ascertain the extent to which technical skill affect Stability of family business in Enugu State Nigeria, to identify the influence of experience on the longevity of family business in Enugu State Nigeria and to determine the extent to which higher education affect the effectiveness of family business in Enugu State Nigeria. The researcher employed survey research design. The questionnaire was structured in five Likert scale, in line with the objectives. The population of the study is one thousand one fifty (1150), while the sample size of 505 was drawn, using Taro Yamani statistical tool. Based on the data collected and analyzed with regression Analysis, the study found that; Technical Skill had positive and significant influence on the Stability of family business in south east, Nigeria. (t-cal = 30.798, p-value = 0.000 > 0.05%). Experience had positive and significant influence on the longevity of family business in south east, Nigeria. (t-cal = 20.451, p-value = 0.000 > 0.05%). Higher Education had positive and significant influence on effectiveness of family business in south east, Nigeria. (t-cal = 38.000, p-value = 0.000 > 0.05%). The findings showed that Firms should verify and validate the job information gathered to ensure that it accurately reflects mission requirements. Based on the information, consider streamlining the organization to generate synergies. Firms should conduct a workforce assessment to determine the current human capital capacity based on the verified job requirements. Firms should develop, verify and validate the proficiency scale so that the points on the scale are criterion-referenced, i.e. able to accurately reflect the level of proficiency required. The proficiency scale should account for gains in human capital from on-the job experience.

Keywords: Human Capital Development; Family Business; Technical Skill; High Education; Job Experience and Enugu Nigeria

Introduction

The world is blessed with large deposits of wealth of both natural and human resources and Nigeria shares in these blessings. Though Nigeria is so richly blessed, her economic achievement is not commensurate. That's why chances still exist for improvement. Austin, (2020), has identified a striking contrast between economic backwardness and potential for wealth. Reasons for lack of economic growth in developing countries have constituted one of the major concerns of researches. For Nigeria's National economy to survive, it depends on the survival, development, growth, and expansion of the family businesses and side by side infant industries. A simple definition of a family business is an entity where the ownership and management of the enterprise is across multiple generations; and where the family members play a key and decisive role in leading the strategic direction and operational management of the company (Kellermanns 2017). Family Businesses account for two-thirds of all businesses around the world. They are responsible for the creation for 70 per cent–90 per cent of global annual GDP and 50 per cent–80 per cent of all jobs. Nwachukwu (2018) stated some of the reasons family business is an opportunity to do what they like doing e.g., own a hotel/restaurant, feed well, serve the public and live comfortably. They regard family business ownership as a means of generating profit thus enriching family members. It seems the best way of getting away satisfying paid employment constraints for family members. It is perceived as a way of preparing for retirements. They wish to emulate successful business that have acquired leadership in family business with the power such leadership earns. It is an alternative when steady paid employment could not be secured by family members. They believe that through family business, they could offer special products or services they have conceived. These people don't feel fulfilled except this desire (family business ownership) is realized.

Human capital generally refers to a repertoire of knowledge, competency, attitude and behavior embedded in an individual (Rastogi, 2019). It has gained increasing recognition among organization and management scholars because of its promise to deliver competitive advantage (Gratton 2017) and secure long-term economic growth (Tomer, 2003). The growing emphasis on human capital in organizations reflects a view that market values depend less on tangible resources and more on intangible resources, particularly human resources (HR) (Edström and Lorange, 2014). The quantum or manner in which human beings can generate and use knowledge and skill toward creating intellectual capital is broadly referred to as human capital. Thus, the higher a person's ability to create more relevant intellectual capital, the higher he or she is considered as of higher human capital. The acquisition of this 'relevant' knowledge is the product of conscious and unconscious interactions between them and other human beings which is often referred to as social capital which facilitates the generation of critical and well entrenched institutionalized knowledge possessed by an organization (organizational capital). Thus, human capital as a concept requires a discussion of other terminologies like the human, intellect, social capital and organizational capital (Armstrong, 2006).

Statement of the Problem

The issues of human capital development are not taken seriously by many family businesses, this is because of the failure to acknowledge the fact that business setting has become very active and as such only those business enterprises with the right informational need in the business times can succeed with the right technological manpower to succeed in modern times. Nigerian family businesses have a slightly lower level of perceived concern about the threat from digital disruption or cyber security vulnerability, compared with global average. According to research carried out by family business survey; 77% of respondents say they plan to pass management to the next generation but only 10% have a robust, documented and communicated succession plan in place. The informal culture found in many family businesses have resulted in a lax approach to training new employees, whether they are family members or not. Physical, emotional and financial problems among family members have greatly impacted on the day-to-day operation of family business in Nigeria today. The informal structure and culture found in many family businesses have led to a lack of documentation, policies, and defined strategy and goals. While family members may not always have the same opinions, they often have similar upbringing and life experiences which may lead to a uniform view of the business, businesses need to have external views of their company and their competition in order to thrive. Again, most Nigerian family business do not give their children effective and efficient training, considering the cost implication of sending them on quality training which result into low productivity. Family traditions, ties, and emotions affect knowledge transfer, commitment, and the motivation Failure to take training and development will lead to stifling growth, lack of productivity and inability to compete favorably in the

industry. Pertinent to the above the study examined the influence of human capital development on the continuity of selected family business in south east, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study will be to examine the influence of human capital development on the continuity of selected family business in Enugu State, Nigeria, while the following specific objectives are;

- i. To ascertain the extent to which technical skill affects stability of family business in Enugu State, Nigeria.
- ii. To identify the influence of experience on the longevity of family business in Enugu State, Nigeria.
- iii. To determine the extent to which higher education affects the effectiveness of family business in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Statement of Research Hypotheses

The following alternative hypotheses would guide the study

- i. Technical skill has positive and significant influence on the Stability of family business in Enugu State Nigeria.
- ii. Experience has positive and significant influence on the longevity of family business in Enugu State Nigeria.
- iii. Higher education has positive and significant influence on effectiveness of family business in Enugu State Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Human Capital Development

The Human Capital Development (HCD) is a three syllabi concept that would be split into two; human-capital (one phrase) and development. The quantum or manner in which human beings can generate and use knowledge and skill toward creating intellectual capital is broadly referred to as human capital (Armstrong, 2006). Thus, the higher a person's ability to create more relevant intellectual capital, the higher he or she is considered as of higher human capital. The acquisition of this 'relevant' knowledge is the product of conscious and unconscious interactions between them and other human beings which is often referred to as social capital which facilitates the generation of critical and well entrenched institutionalized knowledge possessed by an organization (organizational capital). Thus, human capital as concept requires a discussion of other terminologies like the human, intellect, social capital and organizational capital (Armstrong, 2006). According to the resource-based view, human capital is the most valuable and most difficult type of resource to imitate because it is, to a large degree, the product of complex social structures that have been built over time (Barney, 2016). Thanks to their shared histories and close-knit relationships, spanning across two subsystems (family and business), individual family members are, by their very idiosyncratic nature, characterized by being not only valuable and rare but also difficult to imitate and non-substitutable (Sirmon & Hitt, 2013).

Technical Skill

Technical skills refer to the specialized knowledge and expertise needed to accomplish complex actions, tasks, and processes relating to computational and physical technology as well as a diverse group of other enterprises. Those who possess technical skills are often referred to as "technicians," with the expression referring to audio technicians, electronics technicians, market technicians, computer technicians, engineering technicians, and a variety of other designations (Oliver, 2017). Technical skills may also refer to the expertise of a certain type of market participant who uses technical analysis signals to buy and sell stocks, bonds, futures, and other financial instruments (Saedi,

Alipour, Mirzapour & Chaboki, 2012). Technical skills are sets of abilities or knowledge used to perform practical tasks in the areas of science, the arts, technology, engineering, and math. Technical skills typically require the use of certain tools and the technologies required to use those tools (Salim, Ashour & Bontis, 2018). In finance, technical skills may refer to traders and analysts who follow the procedures of technical analysis, using charts, indicators, and patterns to generate buy and sell signals.

Experience

Business experience is any work experience. This can include your experiences in any job or freelance work as well as contributions to family businesses or your own entrepreneurial ventures. On a resume, this is typically listed in chronological order with the name of the business and your role as a heading. Prior experience or knowledge of the entrepreneur is a heavily studied characteristic in entrepreneurial behavior (Yahaya, 2017). Startups frequently emerge from entrepreneurs with lots of acquired knowledge or experience within the subject field. Prior experience helps one to understand the opportunities that exist. The entrepreneur is more familiar with the needs and wants that exist and more apt to identify and recognize an opportunity to that meets those needs or wants (Abdullah, 2014). An experience business puts its customers first and foremost and interacts with them in meaningful ways across all channels. Companies that successfully transform into an experience business will grow and thrive. Those that don't will struggle to catch up. But the effort goes far beyond how you do your digital marketing. It needs to be a business priority with a commitment across your entire organization from your CEO on down. It requires a big-picture, strategic approach to increasing your digital maturity and rethinking most, if not all, of your internal processes (Baah & Jauch, 2019).

Higher Education

Higher education is tertiary education leading to award of an academic degree. Higher education, also called post-secondary education, third-level or tertiary education, is an optional final stage of formal learning that occurs after completion of secondary education (Branco & Bibu, 2014). It represents levels 6, 7 and 8 of the 2011 version of the International Standard Classification of Education structure. Tertiary education at a non-degree level is sometimes referred to as further education or continuing education as distinct from higher education. Higher education, also call post-secondary education, third-level or tertiary education, is an optional final stage of formal learning that occurs after completion of secondary education. This consists of Universities, Colleges and Polytechnics that offer formal degrees beyond high school or secondary school education (Corkin, 2012). The International Standard Classification of Education in 1997 initially classified all tertiary education together in 1997 version of its schema.

Family Business

Family business involves the participation of more than one individual of one family in the ownership of private capital company, with control mechanisms that help to keep the company active and closely monitored across generations. It is the firm whose operations/management decisions are affected by leadership succession of the family members managing the business. According to Yilmazer & Schrank (2006) there are three basic concepts that characterize family businesses. First, the ownership structure is such that at least 50% of the organization 's shares are owned by an individual family. Second, a family business is characterized by the emotional attachment, a family shows towards a business or organization. Third, a family business is characterized by a management structure centered on a central family structure. Cromie & Sullivan (1999) argued that family managers enjoyed increased status, job security and flexibility. Non-family managers perceived themselves as competitive and independent people because they have better academic qualifications and were less likely to be married.

Conceptual Framework

Source: Research model, 2022

Theoretical Review

The Following Theories Will Guide the Study; Human Capital Theory, Resource-Based View Theory and Core Competency Theory

Human Capital Theory

The development of human capital theory started in the 1960s, when Theodore Schultz (who was later, in 1979, awarded the Nobel Prize in Economic Sciences), introduced the idea that “skills and knowledge are a form of capital” (1961). Although Adam Smith had already, in the 18th century, referred to individual abilities as forming part of a country’s capital, Shultz was the first to argue formally against the predominant values and beliefs, which had held scholars back from “looking upon human beings as capital goods” and as “wealth that can be augmented by investment” such as education and training. Schultz also highlighted a connection between human capital and economic growth, by associating investments aimed at enhancing “human capabilities to do productive work” with an increase in their productivity (1961).

Resource-Based View Theory

This study employed the Resource-Based View theory as argued by Wernerfelt, (1984). The theory argues that a firm has the ability to achieve and sustain competitive advantage if it possesses resources that are valuable, rare, imperfectly imitable and non-substitutable. Not all resources are strategically relevant within an organization. The goal of an organization is to ensure it has access to and control of valuable resources by developing and securing all the relevant resources either internally or externally. If a firm possesses critical resources that have strategic value, it is better to retain the activity in-house. On the contrary, if the strategic value of target activities is low and no internal resources are available to perform such activities, it is beneficial for the company to outsource them. For the sustainable competitive advantages firms are forced to rely on a multitude of outside suppliers for parts, software, knowhow and sales and in doing so gain access to valuable resources and external capabilities (Langlois 1990). The argument here fits with the need and factors that lead to outsourcing decisions in firms, whether they are cost reduction, new product/services introduction, focus on core competencies or labour flexibility and how they improve organizational performance. The study is anchored on Resource-based View theory by Wernerfelt, (1984). The theory argues that a firm has the ability to achieve and sustain competitive advantage if it possesses resources

that are valuable, rare, imperfectly imitable and non-substitutable. Not all resources are strategically relevant within a business environment. The goal of a business is to ensure it has access to and control of valuable resources by developing and securing all the relevant resources either internally or externally. If a firm possesses critical resources that have strategic value, it is better to retain the activity in-house. On the contrary, if the strategic value of target activities is low and no internal resources are available to perform such activities, it is beneficial for the business to outsource them.

Empirical Review

Khera (2018) has conducted research to find the relation between Technical Skill and Employee productivity in India. As recently human resource management have become a main focus of many organizations because they considered it as main factor that can help to achieve competitive advantage. Sampling frame was employees of foreign, public & private banks. The purpose of this study is to observe and compare the quality of Technical Skill in different commercial banks in India and also determine how human resource practices contribute to the productivity of employees. Convenience sampling technique and Duncan's mean test have been used to evaluate and analyze the data. Findings of this study have shown that Technical Skill can affect the HRM outcomes such as behavior, attitudes which in a way improve the organizational performance hence relationship between HRM policies and organizational performance influenced through HRM outcomes. Oforegbunam and Okorafor (2018) have carried out research on effects of skills development on the performance of small and medium scaled enterprises in the southeastern region of Nigeria. On the technical skill, educational institutions and participation in training program by employees were used as main factors for human development capacity. Likert 5-point scale was used for the quantification of data. Multiple regression tool used in explore the effects of human capacity developments on the performance. Results of this research show that with the increase of human capital development performance of SME's improved and human capital in SME can be enhanced with 'skills.

Khan (2019) has carried out an empirical study on Technical Skill on organizational performance of oil and gas industry of Pakistan. Data was collected through self-reported questionnaires. Factor analysis and regression analysis was performed for identification and association of these practices. Results of this study have shown that technical skill has positive relation with organizational performance. Adisa, Abdulraheem & Mordi (2018) investigated the challenges of small businesses in Nigeria. An in-depth interview of 152 small businesses in Nigeria and the data set comprised of responses from these business owners were used in the study. The finding also revealed the five major challenges confronting small businesses in Nigeria which are, inexperience, inadequate funding, poor record keeping and information management, inability to distinguish business capital from personal money, lack of crucial infrastructural facilities and lack of proper business and management skills/knowledge. Adedayo & Ojo (2019) presents the impact of work experience and how they affect the sustainability of family businesses in Nigeria. The study adopted a survey design with a population of study limited to the family business owners who are members of the National Association of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (NASME). A stratified sampling technique was used to select the family businesses, from where a random sample of 327 was selected. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation and Multiple Regression were used to analyze the data. The results revealed that there was a strong positive correlation between work experience and firm's sustainability, with an r value of correlation coefficient of 0.86 and a significant level of $P < 0.05 @ 0.000$.

kam, Sena & Ndamsa (2020) carried out a study of factors affecting the sustainability of FOBs in the Northwest and Southwest Regions of Cameroon. A survey-based approach was used through the purposive sampling technique and thirty family businesses were studied using questionnaires and interviews. Both quantitative and qualitative research methods were in data analysis. The results expressed that most of the family trades' initiators do not have experience and do not consider the sustainability of the businesses after they die and hence do not prepare for progression. Amin (2012) assessed the impact of human capital investment on the economic growth of Pakistan, through their research. Secondary data from 2000-2010 was collected from Economic Survey of Pakistan, State Bank of Pakistan & Labor Organization Annual Reports. Data was analyzed through correlation. Results yielded by the analyses showed that primary enrolment rates, higher education enrolment rates & life expectancy were positively related with economic growth. The study also showed that secondary enrolment rates were negatively related with economic growth. Salim (2014) conducted study in Egyptian software companies to assess the relation between

education qualifications and organizational performance in Pakistan. A sample of 38 software companies, out of total 107, was selected; but only 16 companies responded. Data was collected through interviews and questionnaire. Correlation & regression were used for data analysis. It was concluded from analysis that performance of software firms was influenced by the amount of formal education possessed, intelligence, creative ideas, ambition and imitability of the employees.

Methodology

Descriptive research used in this study. Descriptive research is research that attempts to gather facts from a population so as to establish the existing status of the respondents in regards to the variables, Mugenda and Mugenda (2003). A design study is the culmination of a chain of resolutions by a researcher regarding how the research was performed. Surveys are useful in describing the characteristics of a large population. No other research method can provide this broad capability, which ensures a more accurate sample to gather targeted results in which to draw conclusions and make important decisions. The study adopts primary source of data and the data were collected through well-structure questionnaire. The study adopts a five (5) point Linkert scale. The study was carried out in Enugu stated where it selected five family businesses namely GUO Transport Co located at 3, Market Road by Holy Ghost Cathedral (Opp. Ogbete Main Mkt.) Enugu; Peace Mass transit located at PMT Enugu, Ogbete Bus Park and garriki awknanaw; Agofure mass transit; Fine Brothers located at *Fine Brothers* is located at: 16, Railway Line, Trans-Ekulu 400001, Enugu, Nigeria, acharalayout by mayor bustop and Albatina Nigeria located at 17 Zik Ave, Achara, Enugu, Nigeria. The precise population on which data is needed and, in this case, they are members of employees of the five selected from family Business in Enugu State Nigeria. The total population is one thousand one hundred fifty (1150). The sample was considered based on the strength of workers. In determining the sample size, the author used Cochran, (1963) Statistical Tool. The sample sizes are five hundred and five (505). The data was analyzed with the aid of computer software for analyzing data. Descriptive statistics such as frequency distribution, measure of central tendency that is mean, standard deviation was used. To test for hypotheses, the study employed t-test statistics.

The test statistic is calculated as:

$$t = \frac{\bar{X} - \mu}{\frac{s}{\sqrt{n}}}$$

Where

\bar{X}	=	Sample Mean
s^2	=	Sample Variance
μ	=	Population Mean
t	=	Student t-test

With n-2 degree of freedom and 0.05(5%) level of significance.

Decision Rule

It states that if the computed t-value is greater than the theoretical value also known as critical value, the null hypotheses would be rejected and the alternate accepted, but if the computed value is less than the theoretical value, the null hypothesis would not be rejected but the alternate hypothesis would be rejected.

Data Presentation and Discussion of Findings

The data collected for the study were statistically analyzed and presented in tables. In order to answer the research questions and test the hypotheses, the data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequency and percentage counts, mean and standard deviation), regression analysis was used for hypotheses testing.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 1 Distribution and Return of the Questionnaire

<i>Family business</i>	<i>No. of copies of Questionnaire Distributed</i>	<i>No. of copies of Questionnaire Returned</i>	<i>Percentage Returned</i>	<i>No. of copies of Questionnaire not Returned</i>	<i>Percentage not Returned</i>
<i>GUO Transport Co</i>	18	18	3.56	0	0
<i>Cutix Plc</i>	189	180	35.64	9	1.78
<i>Peze Products Limited</i>	152	150	29.70	2	0.39
<i>Jacobs Wines</i>	122	118	23.37	4	0.79
<i>Vital Industries Nigeria</i>	24	24	4.75	0	0
Total	505	490	97.02	15	2.9

Sources: Field Survey, 2022

From the table 1, total of five hundred and five (505) copies of questionnaire were distributed to the selected family business in south East Nigeria; 18 copies of the questionnaire were given to GUO Transport Co, Enugu State after which all copies of questionnaires were returned. A total of 189 copies of questionnaire were given to Cutix Plc after which 180(22%) copies of questionnaire were returned and 9(0.4%) copies of the questionnaire were not returned; A total of 152 questionnaire were given to PEZE Products Limited after which 150(30%) copies of questionnaire were returned and 2(0.4%) copies of the questionnaire were not returned; A total of 122 questionnaire were given to Jacobs Wines after which 118(23%) copies of questionnaire were returned and 2(0.4%) copies of the questionnaire were not returned; A total of 24 questionnaire were given to Vital Industries Nigeria Limited after which all copies of questionnaires were returned.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One

Technical Skill has positive and significant influence on the Stability of family business in south east Nigeria.

Table 2: Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.560	.122		4.578	.000
	Technical Skill	.854	.028	.885	30.798	.000

Dependent Variable: Stability of family business

Source: SPSS output Version 20.

Student's T-Test:

This test was conducted to ascertain the significant status of each of the parameters or variables. In doing this, we employed the two-tail tests which compared the t-calculated for the explanatory variables with the t-tabulated.

Decision Rule: It states that if the probability value of t-test statistics is greater than 5% margin which is the critical value, the alternative hypotheses will be rejected and the null accepted, but if probability value of t-test statistics is less than 5% margin, the alternative hypothesis will be accepted and the null hypothesis rejected.

Decision:

From the analysis in table 4.12; probability value i.e (t-cal = 30.798, p-value = 0.000 < 0.05%). Therefore, we accept alternative hypothesis which states that Technical Skill has positive and significant influence on the Stability of family business in south east Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two

Experience has positive and significant influence on the longevity of family business in south east Nigeria.

Table 3: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.512	.186		2.751	.006
	Experience	.856	.042	.784	20.451	.000

Dependent Variable: Longevity of family business

Source: SPSS output Version 20.

Student’s T-Test:

This test was conducted to ascertain the significant status of each of the parameters or variables. In doing this, we employed the two-tail tests which compared the t-calculated for the explanatory variables with the t-tabulated.

Decision Rule: It states that if the probability value of t-test statistics is greater than 5% margin which is the critical value, the alternative hypotheses will be rejected and the null accepted, but if probability value of t-test statistics is less than 5% margin, the alternative hypothesis will be accepted and the null hypothesis rejected.

Decision

From the analysis in table 4.13; probability value i.e (t-cal = 20.451, p-value = 0.000 < 0.05%). Therefore, we accept alternative hypothesis which states that Experience has positive and significant influence on the longevity of family business in south east Nigeria.

Hypothesis Three

Higher Education has positive and significant influence on effectiveness of family business in south east Nigeria

Table 4: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.593	.098		6.030	.000
	Higher Education	.844	.022	.920	38.000	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Effectiveness of family business

Source: SPSS output Version 20

Student’s T-Test:

This test was conducted to ascertain the significant status of each of the parameters or variables. In doing this, we employed the two-tail tests which compared the t-calculated for the explanatory variables with the t-tabulated.

Decision Rule:

It states that if the probability value of t-test statistics is greater than 5% margin which is the critical value, the alternative hypotheses will be rejected and the null accepted, but if probability value of t-test statistics is less than 5% margin, the alternative hypothesis will be accepted and the null hypothesis rejected.

Decision:

From the analysis in table 4.14; probability value i.e (t-cal = 38.000, p-value = 0.000 < 0.05%). Therefore, we accept alternative hypothesis which states that Higher Education has positive and significant influence on effectiveness of family business in south east Nigeria.

Discussion of Results

Technical Skill and The Stability of Family Business

From the analysis in table 4.12; probability value i.e (t-cal = 30.798, p-value = 0.000 < 0.05%). Therefore we accept alternative hypothesis which states that Technical Skill has positive and significant influence on the Stability of family business in south east Nigeria. This result agreed with the result of Khan (2019) who carried out an empirical study on Technical Skill on organizational performance of oil and gas industry of Pakistan. Results of this study have shown that technical skill has positive relation with organizational performance.

Experience and the Longevity of Family Business

From the analysis in table 4.13; probability value i.e (t-cal = 20.451, p-value = 0.000 < 0.05%). Therefore, we accept alternative hypothesis which states that Experience has positive and significant influence on the longevity of family business in south east Nigeria. This result conforms with the result of Adedayo & Ojo (2019) who evaluated the impact of work experience and how they affect the sustainability of family businesses in Nigeria. The results revealed that there was a strong positive correlation between work experience and firm's sustainability, with an r value of correlation coefficient of 0.86 and a significant level of $P < 0.05 @ 0.000$.

Higher Education and Effectiveness of Family Business

From the analysis in table 4.14; probability value i.e (t-cal = 38.000, p-value = 0.000 < 0.05%). Therefore, we accept alternative hypothesis which states that Higher Education has positive and significant influence on effectiveness of family business in south east Nigeria. This result agreed with the result of Yahaya (2007) who conducted research to explore the effect of education qualifications and development on the efficiency of employees in Nigerian Banks. The study showed that education qualifications enhance the level of employees' performance in an organization.

Summary of Findings

Based on the data collected and analyzed, the study found that:

- i. Technical Skill had positive and significant influence on the Stability of family business in south east Nigeria. (t-cal = 30.798, p-value = 0.000 < 0.05%).
- ii. Experience had positive and significant influence on the longevity of family business in south east Nigeria. (t-cal = 20.451, p-value = 0.000 < 0.05%).
- iii. Higher Education had positive and significant influence on effectiveness of family business in south east Nigeria. (t-cal = 38.000, p-value = 0.000 < 0.05%).

Conclusion

The study examined the influence of human capital development on the continuity of selected family business in South East Nigeria. Based on the findings made, it shows that all the indicators which include technical skill, experience and higher education had positive and significant influence on stability, longevity and effectiveness of family business in south east Nigeria. The findings revealed that technical skill had positive and significant influence on the Stability of family business in south east Nigeria. Experience had positive and significant influence on the longevity of family business in south east Nigeria. Higher education had positive and significant influence on effectiveness of family business in south east Nigeria. Therefore, we conclude that human capital development has a positive and significant influence on the continuity of selected family business in South East Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made.

1. Firms should verify and validate the job information gathered to ensure that it accurately reflects mission requirements. Based on the information, consider streamlining the organization to generate synergies.
2. Firms should conduct a workforce assessment to determine the current human capital capacity based on the verified job requirements.
3. Firms should develop, verify and validate the proficiency scale so that the points on the scale are criterion-referenced, i.e., able to accurately reflect the level of proficiency

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